

Lessons from the history of global policies against malaria and aspects of contemporary developments in global health governance

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Table of content

1	Background and contribution of the paper	2
2	General characteristics of and challenges to global policies against malaria	2
2.1	Interpreting and negotiating the malaria problem	2
2.2	Exit/voice, demonstration projects, and organizational proliferation.....	4
2.3	The dramatic structure of the policy process and the challenge of implementation.....	4
2.4	Layers of the implementation process	7
3	Specific considerations and challenges in the context of eradication.....	7
3.1	The decision as the apparent climax.....	7
3.2	Implementation challenges and unintended consequences.....	9
3.3	Conceptual clarity and practical complexity of eradication	12
4	Present dynamics	13
5	Conclusion.....	17
6	Sources quoted.....	18

1 Background and contribution of the paper

The World Health Organization Global Malaria Program (WHO-GMP) has convened a Strategic Advisory Group on malaria eradication (SAGme). SAGme has the overarching objective to advise WHO “on the feasibility, potential strategies and cost of eradicating malaria over the next decades”.¹ The objective will be reached through a process of analysis and discussion in the course of which insights from different work packages will be synthesised into a final product.²

The present paper contributes to the overall objective of SAGme by providing a socio-political perspective on global policies against malaria. Not least since eradication attempts have failed in the past, the following two questions serve as the starting point of the analysis. First, the overarching question of what lessons regarding the general characteristics of and challenges to global policies against malaria can be learned from history. Second, the more focused sub-question of what specific lessons regarding eradication attempts can be learned. These two questions are addressed by drawing on both primary and on secondary sources. Moreover, the malaria-specific (historical) analysis is complemented with literature on international organizations and global health governance.

Building on the historical analysis, governance literature, as well as findings from SAGme’s fourth meeting, the paper assesses furthermore what opportunities and challenges emerge for global policies against malaria in the context of present dynamics. Since key developments in global health governance have started only recently and are still in the process of unfolding, this part of the analysis relies mainly on primary sources but draws also on further literature on international organizations and global governance. Not only because SAGme advises WHO but also because eradication refers to a global state of affairs while WHO has the constitutional mandate to serve as the directing and coordinating authority on world health, the analysis is conducted with a particular focus on WHO’s past and present role. There are various aspects of the analysis that SAGme can draw upon when finalizing its findings. Key conclusions, including recommendations, are summarized in the final section of this paper.

2 General characteristics of and challenges to global policies against malaria

Dealing with malaria means facing contradictions. The history of malaria control is a story of great successes and huge optimism but also a story of setbacks and failures. From a historical perspective, it is not surprising that the *New York Times* could enthusiastically write in 1919 that “malaria control [was] found to be easy”,³ while, almost a century later, the *World Malaria Report 2017*⁴ indicated that the global fight against malaria was at crossroads and the *World Malaria Report 2018*⁵ suggested that the malaria response had to get back on track. There are various factors that account for this contradictory state of affairs; the subsequently following paragraphs will highlight their socio-political dimension by discussing key elements of global malaria governance.

2.1 Interpreting and negotiating the malaria problem

Malaria is a complex disease that is marked by what scholars of science and technology studies have called “interpretative flexibility”.⁶ This means essentially that different people or different groups of people will interpret the malaria problem differently. There are three interrelated questions in particular, on which they

¹ WHO 2016

² WHO 2019b.

³ *The New York Times* 1919, emphasis removed (the original text is a headline in capital letters).

⁴ WHO 2017d, and Alonso and Noor 2017.

⁵ WHO 2018c.

⁶ Bijker 1995.

might disagree. These three questions and the follow-up questions to which they will often lead are displayed in figure 1:⁷

Figure 1: Interrelated questions that help to identify specific interpretations of the malaria problem

To briefly illustrate the implications of “interpretative flexibility”, it could be recalled that there are several approaches to (or traditions of) malaria control and that three of them have been particularly relevant in the history of malaria control. Each of them has a tendency to interpret the malaria problem in a particular way: there is an entomological approach in the tradition of Ronald Ross, there is a pharmaceutical approach in the tradition of Robert Koch, and there is a socio-medical approach in the tradition of Angelo Celli.⁸ To be sure, the three approaches are not necessarily incompatible but they can still result in conflicting recommendations when it comes to the prioritization of measures against malaria. As a consequence, there has often been disagreement on policies against malaria while the supporters of individual solutions were convinced that they knew the right answer.

What is just as important is the observation that each approach and the concomitant interpretation of the malaria problem depend on the cooperation of specific actors and on the availability of specific resources as is described by the two questions at the bottom: “who should solve the problem” – which implies the question of whose cooperation is needed – and “what is the solution” – which implies the question of what resources are needed. The issue of whose cooperation is needed is a key consideration when it comes to implementation, which will be discussed in more detail below. In this context, it is also important to keep in mind that interpretations of the malaria problem will not only vary across scholarly traditions but also across the various actors and groups of actors that are part of the struggle against malaria. A typical challenge has been that the interpretations at the global level do not capture national and sub-national interpretations. Similarly, those who focus on malaria have often overlooked that malaria is not a priority for everyone. Finally, each interpretation highlights particular aspects of the malaria problem; while this has the advantage to represent malaria as a more readily intelligible problem, it can easily lead to oversimplification that does not pay tribute to alternative interpretations (including the value of alternative solutions) and the overall complexity of malaria. This tension is closely linked to issues such as criticisms of “one-size-fits-all approaches”, the pitfalls of “overconfidence”, or the challenge of “lack of implementation”, which will be touched upon in the subsequently following (sub-)sections.

⁷ This subsection draws on Eckl 2017, where figure 1 appears on page 425.

⁸ While historians of malaria tend to agree on the observation that there are different traditions of malaria control, the empirical variation of the measures against malaria – both over time and across space – can be conceptualized in different ways. For a concise text that contains a table that contrasts three ideal types along the lines mentioned here, see Labisch 2003. For key texts on the history of malaria control that were either written by retrospectively analysing outsiders or provide (self-reflective) accounts by practitioners, see Ackerknecht 1952, Black et al. 1980, Eckl 2010, Farid 1980, Gramiccia and Beales 1988, Jeffery 1976, Litsios 2002, Nájera 1999, Nájera, González-Silva, and Alonso 2011, Packard 2007, Siddiqi 1995, Stepan 2011, and Trigg and Kondrachine 1998.

2.2 Exit/voice, demonstration projects, and organizational proliferation

A second issue that is relevant at this point is the observation that malaria policy has often been shaped by both voice and exit. In particular, the different perspectives on malaria were not only discussed in the abstract in central decision-making fora where the supporters of the different views would raise their *voice*. Rather, following the logic of *exit*-based policy making there has been a tendency to try to “prove” the superiority of one’s own solution to (and interpretation of) the malaria problem through so-called “demonstration projects” or field trials, which were often conducted with a mix of research-related and political goals in mind. Exit-based policy making can take various forms but the unifying feature is that solutions are pursued independent of those who do not support them; at the same time, there is the hope that success would subsequently put pressure on those who originally did not support the solution.⁹ A noteworthy case in point is the much-debated Sardinian campaign whose apparent success was instrumental for the rise of DDT-based antimalarial policies and for the eventual decision to start a global eradication campaign – even though closer inspection reveals that Sardinia was not a clear-cut success story.¹⁰

While exit has the potential advantage that policies can be pursued in the absence of consensus, two recurrent problems of exit-based strategies are particularly noteworthy. First, there is the question of whether the successes in one setting can be reproduced in another setting, or, going one step further, if successes in a circumscribed setting can be up-scaled to larger areas or even to the global level. Second, there is the problem that exit-based strategies tend to be biased towards solutions that have an easily discernible short-term effect that can then be used to persuade others to support the solution. In the context of malaria control, this has often meant that the sustainability of such solutions is not properly assessed and that the influence of long-term changes on malaria prevalence is not systematically investigated. These problems are among the factors that are responsible for the remarkable ups and downs in malaria control, where enthusiasm is followed by pessimism, and they have led to a neglect of systemic change – both at the level of society and at the level of health systems.

While exit has been relevant throughout the history of malaria control, the proliferation of actors, partnerships, and initiatives that accelerated in the 1990s has given it an even more prominent role since the mere existence of alternatives has undermined the formal authority of WHO “to act as the directing and coordinating authority on international health work”.¹¹ To be sure, these various kinds of organisations have, in principle, the potential to complement the work of WHO and one could argue that some of them have closed important gaps; in practice, however, it has often become obvious that different organisations – explicitly or implicitly – promote different interpretations of the malaria problem and that partners can easily become competitors. Even before the 1990s, this ambiguity was evidenced by the in theory complementary but at times complicated relationship between WHO and UNICEF.¹² What this comes down to is that, in the present context, exit plays a key role, not only at the level of field trials but also at an institutional level; it can be the consequence of an intentional creation of alternatives or an unintended side-effect. These developments are not unique to malaria but a challenge in global health governance more broadly,¹³ which raises the general question of whether WHO can at least play an orchestrating role when its directing and coordinating roles are weakened.¹⁴ In other words, WHO is a unique organization in global health governance but its authority has not remained unchallenged and it has to be continuously reaffirmed.

2.3 The dramatic structure of the policy process and the challenge of implementation

In spite of the pervasiveness of exit in global health governance, voice-based policy making in central decision-making fora like the World Health Assembly (WHA) continues to be indispensable. While the general relevance of such decision-making fora is undisputed, the dramatic structure of the policy process leads easily to a misleading image of the process as a whole. Political practitioners, the media, the public,

⁹ On exit and voice, see Hirschman 1981.

¹⁰ P. J. Brown 1999, Logan 1953, Snowden 2006, Stapleton 2004.

¹¹ WHO 1948, 100.

¹² For examples of cooperation and rivalry between WHO and UNICEF, see Lee 2009, 19, 39, 67–68, 74–75, 81, 108. For a discussion of overlapping effective mandates of health-related United Nations organizations, which anticipated problems that intensified later, see Lee et al. 1996.

¹³ On the shift from “international” to “global” health, see T. M. Brown, Cueto, and Fee 2006. On “global health governance”, see Lee and Kamradt-Scott 2014.

¹⁴ On the varying degrees to which WHO can serve as an orchestrator, see Hanrieder 2015b.

and academia, are united by their tendency to overestimate the relevance of one particular phase in the policy process, namely the decision in the narrow sense of the term. In domestic politics, the focus is on decisions that turn bills into law and, in international politics, the focus is on decisions that turn drafts into final agreements, resolutions, and so forth. While the notion that such decisions represent the climax of the policy process is not entirely wrong, it is still misleading since it focuses on the end point of Phase II and overlooks the other phases of the process that are described in figure 2.¹⁵

Figure 2: The Three Main Phases of the Policy Process

Two points that follow from this observation are of particular relevance for the present discussion; the first one applies to any policy process, the second one is specific to global health policy. First of all, there is a general tendency to overlook Phase III as the phase that comes after the decision and hence a tendency to neglect the role of implementation, which is a complex process in its own right. Secondly, and as a consequence, the specifics of global health governance that were discussed in the previous subsection and the particularities of WHO as a political system are easily forgotten: most of the decisions that are taken with a view to global health policies are not legally binding, and if they are, they are binding only for some actors. A disregard for such particularities will quickly reinforce the overestimation of the relevance of individual decisions, while the majority of WHA resolutions, which are the most common output of WHO decision-making, are essentially expressions of a collective will that cannot be enforced upon individual member states.¹⁶

Typically, WHA resolutions address different sets of actors whose behaviour is relevant for the purpose of implementation. The most common actors that are addressed in WHA resolutions on global health policies are WHO's secretariat (usually in the form of the Director-General), member states, other international organisations, and non-state actors. The key point is that most resolutions are binding mainly from the perspective of WHO but less so for its member states – let alone for external actors. This can be illustrated with the specific wording that is commonly used in resolutions. The 68th WHA, for example, which adopted the *Global Technical Strategy (GTS) for Malaria 2016–2030*,¹⁷ requested the Director-General, urged member states, as well as invited and called upon partners to contribute to the implementation of the strategy.¹⁸ In other words, while there is a general tendency to view the decisions as such as the most important part of the policy process, this tendency is particularly problematic in the context of decisions taken by WHO that has a long history of relying on non-binding policy instruments and whose governance bodies have no direct formal authority over the various external organizations that have proliferated in the past two decades.

¹⁵ Figure 2 builds on Eckl, n.d. For a critical overview of different models of the policy process, see Jann and Wegrich 2014.

¹⁶ The kinds of decisions that the WHA takes and the rules under which they are taken depend on context. While Article 23 of the WHO Constitution has rarely been invoked, WHA resolutions on global health policies are commonly nevertheless of a recommendatory nature vis-à-vis WHO's member states. On this point, see Burci and Vignes 2004, 142. For a more extensive discussion of global health law, the continuum between “hard” and “soft” law, the degree to which agreements are binding or non-binding, as well as the role of formal and informal norms, see Burci and Vignes 2004, Hein and Moon 2013, Gostin and Sridhar 2014, and Kates and Katz 2011.

¹⁷ WHO 2015d.

¹⁸ WHO 2015e.

The general observation that implementation is a challenge in its own right applies also to the other products of WHO's normative work, i.e. to documents such as guidelines. The development of guidelines is normally conducted by the secretariat (and external experts) without formally involving member states and these documents (or publications) are not necessarily adopted by the governance bodies.¹⁹ In other words, they are the product of a different kind of decision-making process but this does not mean that implementation is any easier. Quite to the contrary, evaluations of the impact of WHO's publications and of WHO's normative function have highlighted that normative processes go beyond the publication of documents and that there is a need to improve the actual uptake.²⁰

While the non-enforceable character of WHO's normative documents underscores the point that implementation cannot be taken for granted, it is worth-while mentioning that the predominance of "soft law" in international health is not a coincidence. Rather, it has been seen as a way to get the agreement of member states to ambitious and aspirational documents that were considered by WHO's governance bodies. Similarly, it has been regarded as an enabling factor for the separation of professional expertise from various other concerns of member states, including foreseeable challenges to and domestic conflicts around implementation. Additionally, it has been highlighted that there needs to be flexibility to adopt internationally agreed documents to national and subnational context. Finally and importantly, even though most of WHO's normative documents are non-binding, member states do react to them. In other words, in many cases, "soft law" makes a difference and, as will be discussed further in the next subsection, it is primarily in those moments when implementation is found wanting that the non-enforceable character of WHO's normative guidance comes to the fore.

Historically, there were some interesting episodes at which WHO's governance bodies explicitly debated the fact that there can be a trade-off between the degree to which a document is binding and the degree to which it can be ambitious and aspirational, which may include the desire to give strict and detailed guidance that (some) member states find difficult to agree to. In the well-known case of the "International Code of Marketing of Breast-Milk Substitutes", they concluded that it was best to adopt the Code as a non-binding recommendation (as opposed to a binding regulation) and, in return, to agree to it by consensus and to maintain provisions that not all member states supported.²¹ It is important to keep this potential trade-off in mind when the question is addressed what needs to be done in a specific area of global health.

While the non-binding character of WHO's normative documents is expected to have the ambiguous consequence to make consensus at the global level easier and implementation less reliable, there is another aspect of the policy process that is easily overlooked if the analysis stops once the decision in the narrow sense of the term has been taken. As the section on the interpretative flexibility of the malaria problem indicated, each solution requires the cooperation of specific actors but this does not imply that they share a common interpretation of the malaria problem; since only a subset of the actors whose cooperation will be needed or who feel otherwise affected by the decision has access to international governance bodies and expert committees, all others can raise their voice only in the course of the implementation process.²² This applies to local populations in particular and, as we will also see below, decision-making on malaria has a long history of engaging the local level too late. The practical challenge that emerges from the confrontation of divergent interpretations of the malaria problem in the course of implementation is that it is too quickly dismissed as an irritating obstacle rather than an important and expectable aspect of global health governance.²³

¹⁹ For insightful reactions at the Executive Board to an attempt to change this practice, see WHO 2015a, WHO 2015b, 1–2, and WHO 2015c, 35–40.

²⁰ Ennis et al. 2016, and Kruse and Kaya 2017.

²¹ In the end, the Code was still rejected by one member state (while two more voted against it unintentionally and clarified their position later) but the general approach to use the non-binding character as a tool to reach consensus seems to have worked. For the discussions during the World Health Assembly, see WHO 1981, 187–201, 212, for an early scholarly assessment, see Sikkink 1986, for the original advice by the legal counsel as opposed to the consensus-seeking rationale that prevailed, see Burci and Vignes 2004, 144.

²² For a more detailed but still concise discussion this phenomenon and its implications, see Wiener 2017.

²³ Heggenhougen, Hackethal, and Vivek 2003.

2.4 Layers of the implementation process

Once the danger of stopping the analysis at the level of the decision has become clear, the question emerges, how implementation should be conceptualized. A common proposition from the literature is to distinguish between three interrelated layers at which the effects of (political) organisations on their environment can be analysed: output, outcome, and impact.²⁴ “Output” comprises the immediate results of the activities of an organization; in the case of WHO, this includes resolutions, agreed policy documents such as global strategies, and all other types of normative publications. “Outcome” refers to the behavioural changes by target actors as described above. “Impact” covers the relevant changes in the policy area; in the case of malaria, a typical measure for impact would be the case incidence rate.

This conceptualization of implementation helps to understand three challenges. First of all, the link from output via outcome to impact is primarily an assumption. The link can be broken for a variety of reasons but a typical problem is that the target actors do not respond to the output documents at all or not in expected ways. As was just discussed, a typical reason for this broken link is the non-binding character of many output documents. But even if the target actors do respond to the output documents in the desired way, their behavioural change might not lead to the anticipated impact – for example because the intervention that was implemented did not work in the specific setting. The second challenge is that it is often not easy to measure what would be of interest, which might lead to a reliance on estimates. While outcome tends to be particularly difficult to measure, this applies even to impact, as has often been debated in the case of malaria.²⁵ The third and closely related challenge is that there will at times be disagreement on the question of what the relevant changes are that should be measured.

What this comes down to is that it is actually demanding to produce reliable knowledge about the implementation process. This is an important issue since such knowledge is meant so serve as the basis for an evaluation and refinement of the implementation process and could even lead to a revision of the decision that started it. By contrast, if it is unclear what the target actors are doing and if it is unclear if the proposed behavioural change has the desired impact, it remains nebulous what changes should be made to the organizational output documents. In other words, the analytical separation of output, outcome, and impact is an important first step but might not deliver easy answers regarding the status of implementation. It helps to avoid hasty conclusions but might also make it even more obvious how difficult it can be in practice to discern why certain targets are not met or why, for example, global policies against malaria get off track.

3 Specific considerations and challenges in the context of eradication

The history of malaria and its control has already been analysed in various scholarly publications and the failed attempt to eradicate malaria is commonly an important aspect of the historical discussions.²⁶ For the present purpose, there is no need to aim for an exhaustive list of factors that account for the failure of eradication; rather, there are three aspects of these discussions that complement the insights from the previous section and warrant closer inspection. First, there is the decision of 1955 to start a global eradication campaign. What strategies and arguments were used in order to justify the decision, how strongly was it supported, and to what degree was it understood what kind of commitment the decision entailed? Second, there is the implementation process that followed after the decision of 1955. What implementation challenges emerged after the strategic reorientation towards eradication in 1955 and to what extent did they differ from the ones that emerged after the re-examination in 1969? Third, there is the very concept of eradication. What general lessons regarding eradication can be drawn from the analysis?

3.1 The decision as the apparent climax

Ever since the mosquito-parasite theory of malaria has been established, people fighting the disease have

²⁴ See, for example, Rittberger, Zangl, and Kruck 2012.

²⁵ There have been repeated discussions in this regard in the *World Malaria Reports* (see, for example, WHO 2013, 60–68, box 8.2 in particular). For a critical engagement with the generation of malaria-related data that references further literature, see Tichenor 2017.

²⁶ For key texts on the history of malaria control, see footnote 8.

been fascinated and inspired by the idea that the disease could actually be eradicated. The degree to which they considered it practically feasible to eradicate malaria has however varied. As a consequence, turning points in grand strategy become particularly interesting for the present purpose. The most obvious case in point is 1955 since this is the year when the decision was taken to make malaria eradication a direct short-term goal – rather than treating a world free of malaria as a long-term vision. There are four approaches in particular that were used by the supporters of eradication in order to overcome resistance to their interpretation of malaria and its solution.

First of all, exit played an important role. Most notably, the local “eradication” (as it was called at the time)²⁷ of malaria in one setting (e.g. Sardinia) was used as evidence for the possibility of “eradication” in other settings – or even globally. Exit was also relevant in the sense that, by the time WHO addressed the issue, the Pan American Sanitary Organization (PASO) had already decided to independently start a regional “eradication” campaign in the Americas, which posed the threat that WHO would be left behind. Secondly, proponents of eradication made the economic argument that it would save costs in the long run to eradicate the disease. Thirdly, control programmes were described as unsustainable. In particular, the historically successful and continuously practiced ways of controlling malaria without the use of DDT were eclipsed and the argument was made that, in light of the emergence of resistances, DDT as the key tool against malaria had to be saved. This rationale and the concomitant sense of urgency were explicitly taken up in the text of the resolution that started the campaign; the text stated that the emerging resistances to DDT would warrant an intensification of “plans of nation-wide malaria control so that malaria eradication may be achieved and the regular insecticide-spraying campaigns safely terminated before the potential danger of a development of resistance to insecticides in anopheline vector species materializes”.²⁸ Fourthly, the implications of the decision to start a global eradication campaign and the difficulties of eradication, including its costs, were downplayed. The fourth approach warrants closer inspection since the historical record suggests that it is a rather risky approach in the sense that systematically disregarding implementation challenges increases the danger of failure.

While the approach to downplay implications and challenges has various facets, its underlying logic can be illustrated with the discussions on malaria eradication that took place at the decisive World Health Assembly in 1955.²⁹ The proposal on malaria eradication was introduced to the responsible committee by Paul Russell (from the Rockefeller Foundation but in his capacity as WHO Consultant on Malaria). In his introductory remarks, Russell explained the rationale for the proposal, which included arguments such as long-term cost saving and the threat of resistance. What is particularly interesting is that he highlighted the forthcoming need to formulate a global plan (while he could have elaborated on the foreseeable implications of the draft resolution instead) and that he presented the scope of the decision as a narrow budgetary question: “In simple terms the question facing the Committee was whether or not it should recommend certain additional provisions in the budget to enable WHO to exercise effective leadership in the attempt to eradicate malaria”.³⁰

In the discussion, several speakers returned to this budgetary issue but many expressed also more general reservations regarding both the content of the proposal and the rushed nature of the decision making. When Russell got the opportunity to respond at the end of discussion, he concluded his intervention by returning to the budgetary question and linked it with the threat that WHO might be left behind: “It was important that WHO should maintain its leadership in the campaign to eradicate malaria and the Director-General was requesting only a very modest sum for that purpose”.³¹ In this context, downplaying means that Russell focused on the 309’484 USD that the committee was considering within the context of the WHO budget, which is a tiny sum if compared to the amount of money that was actually mobilized and spent during the campaign.³² In other words, the indirect consequences of the decision were of a radically different scale but

²⁷ At the time, the term eradication was used in a less precise sense than today since no clear distinction was made between eradication and elimination. This could also explain why successes in one setting were quickly seen as evidence for global feasibility. In order to account for the historical use in terminology, the present text speaks at times of “eradication” even though contemporary terminology would suggest “elimination”.

²⁸ WHO 1955d.

²⁹ WHO 1955a, 1955c, 1955b.

³⁰ WHO 1955a, 199.

³¹ WHO 1955a, 206.

³² On the financial dimension of the campaign, see Gramiccia and Beales 1988, 1346–47, 1350–52, Nájera 1999, 66–82,

not at the centre of attention. Also more general challenges to eradication and possible unintended consequences of a global eradication campaign are pushed to the margins if the focus is on the immediate budgetary consequences. The relevance of such manoeuvres and of the way in which the decision was framed should not be underestimated. In particular, delegates found it difficult to visibly object to such a formidable goal even when they questioned the urgency and the feasibility of the vaguely defined plan. As a consequence, a large part of the criticism was expressed only in private talks and several of those delegates who had criticised the proposal nevertheless voted in its favour.³³

The scope of the decision and the actual challenge remained nebulous also in a second sense. As indicated above, Russell alluded to it but did not consider it as problematic: when the World Health Assembly passed the resolution to start the campaign, no strategy had been developed yet and it was unclear what the campaign would eventually look like. Moreover, there was no historical precedent that would have helped to appreciate the decision's implications. As a consequence, few aspects could be critically assessed. The confusion around the question of what was actually being decided on can be seen rather clearly from the records of the proceedings that show in particular that it remained entirely opaque to what extent Africa was going to be included in the campaign. But also once a strategy had been developed,³⁴ the potential obstacles were still downplayed in the sense that the impression was maintained that eradication could be achieved within a circumscribed time frame and budget. An interesting case in point is the brochure *Malaria Eradication: A Plea for Health* that constituted what would now be called the investment case for malaria eradication.³⁵ The financial and temporal assumptions (or promises) proved fatal when the campaign encountered difficulties and ultimately ran short of funding. What was particularly problematic – but not necessarily surprising – was the absence of a plan B or fall-back option in case the campaign would not meet its goal.

One conclusion from this is that the inherent tension between “selling” and sustainably executing an eradication campaign should be acknowledged. The danger of downplaying the challenges and the political commitment that eradication requests could prove fatal. As the discussions on the Sardinian campaign have shown, the cost and duration of eradication campaigns are very likely to expand well beyond the anticipated limits, which led John Logan, who had long been in charge of the Sardinian campaign, to conclude that such projects “should not be rigidly confined by time, finance or methods”.³⁶ In other words, unless there is a clearly defined fall-back option, starting an eradication campaign implies the political commitment to erase the disease *at any cost* – and not at a fixed price. Supporters of an eradication campaign might also have underestimated the problem that the realm of relevant counterfactuals for political authorities and other actors involved is much broader than a comparison between malaria control and malaria eradication. From their perspective, any money spent on malaria creates opportunity costs since it could also be spent elsewhere. Moreover, funding as such is not the only challenge that has to be overcome. While the potential technical-biomedical obstacles in general and the problem of resistances in particular are well known, let us now turn to a set of socio-political points that are relevant in this context.

3.2 Implementation challenges and unintended consequences

As discussed above, for an analysis of the effects of the decisions of international organizations, it is helpful to distinguish between output, outcome, and impact. Similarly, it is important to acknowledge that the failure to achieve a campaign's goals can in principle be interpreted as the consequence of a broken link between output and outcome or as a broken link between outcome and impact or both. In the first case, the target actors did not behave as requested and, in the second case, the requested behaviour did not have the desired consequences. The triad of output, outcome, and impact provides a useful heuristic device even though it is notoriously difficult to fit complex empirical processes into the scheme and to actually capture or measure the empirical realities. Finally, while this scheme does not automatically include the systematic search for unexpected (external) developments or for unintended consequences, these aspects can still be integrated into the analysis.

and Siddiqi 1995, 171–73.

³³ Gramiccia and Beales 1988, 1345.

³⁴ WHO 1957.

³⁵ WHO 1958.

³⁶ Logan 1953, 301.

If the implementation process that followed after the decision of 1955 is analysed along these lines, some well-known themes appear in a new light and, together with some less frequently told aspects, lead to a complex overall picture. A recurrent theme in the literature is that the global eradication campaign was conducted as a highly rigid and inflexible one-size-fits-all approach that was expected to succeed primarily by spraying DDT in a uniform manner. If the history of the eradication campaign is told along these lines, the problem was not so much that countries (and national malaria programmes) as the main target actors did not follow WHO guidance. Rather, it was the guidance that was flawed since it did not pay tribute to local realities and since it offered initially no response to the emergence of resistances. In other words, the requested behaviour (outcome) did not lead to the desired impact. A related line of criticism would highlight that the campaign was generally ill-prepared for unexpected challenges, including repeatedly prolonged schedules, and exploding costs.

A slightly different picture emerges if those authors are taken seriously who emphasise that not all countries followed the guidance as planned – either because they were not able to or because they were not willing to. First, there was an increasing number of “newly independent countries”, from Africa in particular, who joined WHO in the years after the campaign had started. While most of them were eager to start an eradication campaign, they often lacked the prerequisites and capacities for it. What this group of countries demonstrated rather clearly, however, was that the campaign had not been planned with the most difficult areas in mind and that there was no real guidance available for them. The manner, in which the World Health Assembly reacted after some years, was to introduce an additional pre-eradication phase to its originally four-phased eradication plan.³⁷ Second, there were countries that were accused of merely relabelling their control programmes to eradication programmes and/or pursuing eradication only half-heartedly. The behaviour of both the first and the second group of countries is often explained with the new financial incentive structure that had been created by shifting funding from control to eradication. Regardless of prerequisites, capacity, and will, it appeared financially attractive to embrace eradication.³⁸ Interestingly, this earmarking of funding added a coercive dimension to the normative documents of WHO but did not always secure the desired results. Third, Venezuela in particular has been described as a case where the national authorities deviated deliberately from WHO guidance but could achieve great successes.³⁹ In this case, the national authorities worked on the assumption that the requested behaviour change would not lead to the desired impact and tailored measures against malaria to the specific context.

If the predominant account of a rigid approach and these observations are taken together, one can say that WHO’s technical guidance was often able to achieve the requested behaviour change but there was also variation across countries and, in the case of conflict, WHO could not enforce its guidance upon member states. Moreover, WHO did not systematically support countries to adapt WHO guidance to local circumstances. This was primarily possible in a country like Venezuela that looked back on its own history of malaria control and had the necessary knowledge and resources to pursue its own plan. Similarly, there was no systematic approach to allow for institutional learning and large scale revisions at the global level. Rather, there were only reluctant and small adaptations. While these observations suggest that the campaign could have been organized better, it seems likely that global eradication would not have been achieved in any case; the question is rather, if better results in terms of malaria morbidity and mortality could have been achieved in some areas, if the campaign could have been re-examined earlier, and if the negative consequences – following from its unsustainability in particular – could have been mitigated.

While WHO’s technical guidance, in spite of its non-binding character, was often successful in inducing behavioural change at country level, the situation was more difficult in the case of global resource mobilization. Actually, it was the drying up of voluntary funding at the global level in particular that led to the eventual turning away from eradication.⁴⁰ This renewed change in grand strategy went hand in hand with a massive reduction of the size of the malaria programme at WHO which had to be increasingly financed via WHO’s regular budget that was based on member states’ assessed contributions.⁴¹ The re-examined strategy

³⁷ WHO 1961. See also Gramiccia and Beales 1988, 1351, and Nájera 1999, 56.

³⁸ Siddiqi 1995, 144–45.

³⁹ Litsios 1998.

⁴⁰ The strategic relevance of the global level notwithstanding, resource mobilization at country level was considerable (Gramiccia and Beales 1988, 1346–47, 1350–52, Nájera 1999, 66–82, and Siddiqi 1995, 171–73).

⁴¹ For a table that shows the shift from voluntary funds to the regular budget, see Gramiccia and Beales 1988, 1350.

that was adopted by the World Health Assembly in 1969 has been praised for its more flexible approach but flexibility proved to lead to its own implementation challenges: first, it was often not understood what the precise implications of the change in grand strategy were and, second, the behavioural change of target actors in each country (outcome) could not be monitored and evaluated against one common frame of reference.⁴² While there are good epidemiological, social, cultural, and political reasons for granting flexibilities to national campaigns, the sound implementation of flexible provision requires actually more resources and capacities – both at the national and at the global level. But not only were the resources cut down but also became an unintended consequence of the eradication campaign ever more obvious: the anticipated end of malaria had led to a neglect of research on malaria and of education in malariology. As some people would formulate it later and as Lewis Hackett had jokingly foreseen in 1948: the eradication campaign had eradicated the malariologist.⁴³ In light of these considerations, it appears little surprising that there were recurrent complaints that the re-examined strategy was not properly implemented.⁴⁴

The discussions at different World Health Assemblies suggest that both after 1955 and after 1969 member states did not always know what exactly was expected from them – either because the expectations were unrealistic or because too much room for interpretation was given.⁴⁵ This missing link between output and outcome has to be seen as an independent source of challenges for malaria control while the missing link between outcome and impact has been discussed extensively (the problem of resistances and epidemiological variation across space are cases in point). One consequence at a practical level was that apparent turning-point resolutions were often followed by various other resolutions that addressed the problem of interpretation and implementation. This questions the idea that radical change was actually induced by a single resolution but highlights the point that both the strategic shift towards eradication and the strategic shift away from eradication led to complex and difficult follow-up processes that were necessary in order to readjust the system as a whole. By the same token, many of the negative consequences of the eradication campaign occurred not so much in the course of its lifetime but during and after the post-eradication transition.

What has to be added to this discussion of implementation is the more general observation that the perspectives, roles, and contributions of affected countries and populations were continuously overlooked in the policy-making processes and, as a consequence, the decisions at the global level did not necessarily overlap with local needs and priorities. It is noteworthy that this challenge had been known since the early days of malaria control and already the representatives of the Rockefeller Foundation had noted the divergent priorities between malariologists and affected populations. During the Sardinian campaign, for example, two measures were taken that were not warranted from an entomological or epidemiological perspective but promised to rally local support: first, residual spraying was organised in such a way that it would not only kill mosquitoes but also house flies that annoyed people; the prospect of getting rid of this nuisance compelled a householder more “to be put to the trouble of having his house sprayed” than the nocturnal and thus less visible mosquitoes; the second measure that was taken for “public relations” purposes, as it was called, was that spraying was even undertaken in areas in which “malaria was not a serious problem”.⁴⁶ While voices at the sub-national level will find it particularly challenging to be heard at the global level, governments are often incentivised by global funding structures to formally embrace policies that they do not fully support. This makes it not only difficult to take their views into consideration but poses also a challenge for implementation.⁴⁷

An important conclusion that could be drawn from these and some of the earlier findings is that the views of malaria-affected countries and populations have to be more systematically included in the first two phases of

⁴² Farid 1980, and Nájera 1999, 60–63.

⁴³ In an address at a congress on tropical medicine and malaria, Hackett had commented on the successes by Fred Soper and others against malaria in the following manner: “And Dr. Soper may even now be preparing for his next big campaign, to eradicate malariologists” (Hackett 1948, 14). See also Balter 2000 and Jeffery 1976, 364.

⁴⁴ For example, resolution WHA31.45 (1978) states explicitly that it is regrettable that “most of the recommendations in resolution WHA22.39 adopted by the Twenty-second World Health Assembly when it re-examined the global strategy for malaria eradication, and in subsequent resolutions of the Executive Board and Health Assembly, have not been adequately implemented” (WHO 1978).

⁴⁵ Moreover, countries were not always convinced of the proposed policies.

⁴⁶ See Logan 1953, 31 and 261.

⁴⁷ Gramiccia and Beales 1988, 1375.

the policy process and that their crucial roles in and contributions to the third phase have to be more clearly acknowledged. While the support of the international community is often at the centre of attention, affected countries and populations are the ones who will ultimately implement policies through behavioural change, which includes increasingly the need to mobilize substantial financial resources at the national level and not everyone wants to see these resources being spent on malaria control. A focus on affected countries implies also the need to move away from a naïve understanding where these countries are seen as a monolithic group. Both at the domestic level of each of the countries and among countries, the perspectives on malaria will vary. For example, it is much easier for a country that already fulfils most of the requirements that follow from an output document to agree to the document than it is for a country that has to make a major effort in order to get into this direction. By the same token, countries that have eliminated malaria or are close to doing so have a much larger stake in global eradication than those countries that are far from elimination and might face various other (health) challenges at the same time. Such considerations can obviously also be applied to all other actors in the malaria space. As indicated before, the historical record and the notion of “interpretative flexibility” suggest that some actors cannot wait to announce an eradication campaign while others will consider it a risky undertaking that has to be avoided.

3.3 Conceptual clarity and practical complexity of eradication

To be sure, the global malaria eradication campaign has had its successes and positive consequences. At the same time, it would not have been necessary to start a global *eradication* campaign to achieve successes in malaria *control*. The eradication campaign by contrast contributed to the well-known ups and downs in the struggle against malaria and after the initial euphoria, a long period of neglect and even malaria resurgence followed. Had it not been for the successful smallpox eradication campaign, the whole idea of eradication would probably have been discredited by the late 1980s.⁴⁸ Smallpox was eradicated, however, and at least in principle eradication promises to also solve the malaria problem conclusively. At an abstract level, the very idea of eradication is of such conceptual clarity that there will be little opposition to the notion as such. The problem is rather that an eradication campaign (as opposed to the end-stage of having achieved eradication) does not automatically solve the general challenges of global malaria governance. This includes both the complexity of malaria as such and various other aspects – like the issue of mobilizing sufficient amounts of voluntary funding, or the issue of systematically implementing and simultaneously tailoring WHO’s normative guidance. Some of the challenges, for example the financial requirements, will even intensify during an eradication campaign and since there tends to be a negative correlation between the degree to which output documents are aspirational and the degree to which they are legally binding, one should assume that commitment to a global eradication effort will not be enforceable. Those whose cooperation is needed for the provision of this particular solution to the malaria problem will have to be continuously persuaded that it is worth the effort. Overall, the key tension is probably that eradication convinces with its conceptual clarity but entails practical complexity.

Precisely because eradication is such an intuitively convincing concept, the historical record suggests that it is important to clarify the characteristics, implications (e.g. in terms of the required behavioural change), and dangers of a strategic shift towards eradication. This promises to enhance the chances for actual implementation once such a strategic shift occurs and to reduce the negative consequences if the effort fails. As the historical record also shows, successfully passing a resolution is one thing but successfully implementing it is another thing. The fact that the shift towards eradication was not visibly and strongly resisted did not automatically imply that it was fully supported. Generally speaking, there was often a concern that rejecting eradication as a target could undermine its status as a vision and there have also been financial incentives that led to a focus on the opportunities rather than the challenges of an eradication campaign.⁴⁹

⁴⁸ In her history of the idea of disease eradication, Nancy Stepan (2011) highlights the relevance of smallpox in this regard. See also Henderson 1998.

⁴⁹ Obviously, eradication promises that the need to invest in malaria control will come to an end. Moreover, an eradication campaign promises to unleash additional resources. Both arguments matter in principle from the perspective of global donors as well as from the perspective of malaria-affected countries. However, they tend to look at them from different perspectives. This applies to the second argument in particular: global donors try to use their own resources in a way that leverages resource mobilization at the national level while affected countries agree to global policies in the hope that it will unleash additional global funding.

Unless they constitute a mere adjustment in wording, shifts at the level of grand strategy have massive ramifications and a complex system like global malaria governance will require time and effort to react to it. Historically, both the global shift towards eradication and the global shift away from eradication demonstrated the challenges that come along with the ensuing transitions. Moreover, there are specific dangers related to a shift towards eradication that include underestimated costs as well as the premature reduction of professional education and research. Both are linked to a highly deceptive aspect of eradication: its promise to provide a conclusive solution is easily confused with the assertion that it would be possible to plan the end date and, consequently, to determine the overall resource requirements – including financial resources, knowledge, and human resources.

Considering furthermore that existing goals and targets are already ambitious and require an extra effort in order to put malaria control back on track, it seems questionable that turning eradication into a direct goal would add much value. Moreover, it has to be acknowledged that the very process of reformulating grand strategy as well as the task of getting agreement on it absorb resources; alternatively, these resources could be used to help to implement and to tailor policies that have already been agreed on as well as to address pressing problems of malaria control. The current strategy offers an agreed platform for global malaria control while also providing flexibility. This flexibility can be used in order to react to unforeseen challenges and in order to harness current opportunities. While we will turn to potential opportunities in the next section, the recent “High burden to high impact” approach provides a prime example of a targeted response within the existing strategy.⁵⁰ Following an incremental approach and harnessing flexibility gives the opportunity to aim for progress along the ambitious lines that have already been agreed on while making fine-grained adjustments where needed. Instead of readjusting the strategic setting, the multidirectional communication process around implementation challenges could be intensified. This would also give the opportunity to work on the broader determinants of malaria which promises to make malaria control more sustainable and to assure that time is on the side of malaria control and working against the disease.⁵¹

4 Present dynamics

In terms of practical feasibility, malaria eradication faces a multitude of challenges. From this perspective, it is little surprising that malaria was not considered as a prime candidate for eradication when, in the aftermath of the successful smallpox eradication campaign, experts took a comparative approach and developed criteria for the eradicability of diseases and conditions.⁵² At the same time, the most recent SAGme meeting suggests that the conceptual feasibility of malaria eradication remains intact.⁵³ In other words, there is no need to abandon malaria eradication as a vision. The question is rather how malaria control can move forward. An incremental approach along the lines that were suggested towards the end of the previous section promises to pay tribute to the practical challenges of malaria control without precluding the possibility that eradication could ever be achieved. Following up on these ideas, this section will address the question of to what extent and under what conditions present dynamics in global health governance could be harnessed as opportunities for the global struggle against malaria. This includes also the issue of how known challenges could be mitigated.

The current transformation of WHO is particularly relevant. The overall agenda for this process was set out in the 13th General Programme of Work (GPW13) that was approved by the World Health Assembly in 2018.⁵⁴ The implementation of GPW13 is still under way and it is consequently too early to comprehensively assess the practical consequences. It is, however, possible to highlight which aspects are particularly relevant from the perspective of the analysis that was presented in the preceding sections. A general theme of GPW13 is that WHO has to become more results-oriented and that the effects of WHO’s work have to be more

⁵⁰ The approach was discussed at a recent meeting of the Malaria Policy Advisory Committee (MPAC) of WHO. For key features of the approach and comments by MPAC, see WHO 2019i, 4–5.

⁵¹ Degarege et al. 2019.

⁵² Stepan 2011, 11, 256.

⁵³ WHO 2019b.

⁵⁴ WHO 2018b and WHO 2019g.

systematically measured and improved upon.⁵⁵ The overall concern to assess the public health effects of WHO's work at country level has certainly its merits and can be harnessed also for the purpose of malaria control even though it immediately raises questions like: what to measure, how to measure it, how to account for unintended and unexpected consequences, as well as how to capture marginalized (often local) perspectives on these effects. Similarly, a lot of WHO's work might not lead to immediate effects at country level but can still be valuable; this applies in particular, if WHO's normative guidance serves a critical function and identifies gaps between what is done (globally and nationally) and what would be required from WHO's standpoint. Such caveats notwithstanding, from the perspective of malaria control, there are three transformational aspects of the GPW13 in particular that warrant closer inspection: improvement of WHO's normative work, increased attention to the work of country offices, and the WHO impact framework.

When it comes to the improvement WHO's normative work, malaria seems to have served the role of a pathfinder. As discussed in the most recent meeting of the Malaria Policy Advisory Committee (MPAC) of WHO, the policy-making and guidance-development process that is under the auspices of the Global Malaria Programme (GMP) has already undergone a reform that is in line with the GPW13 agenda and aims ultimately at making WHO normative guidance "more useful" for member states.⁵⁶ The changes that have been introduced will still have to stand the test of time but there is reason to believe that they can help to address some of the challenges of the implementation process that were discussed above. The envisioned changes include large goals like improved uptake and small steps such as the introduction of a "Compendium of WHO Malaria Guidance" that gives an overview of the multiple normative documents that address malaria-related issues ranging from the overall global strategy to the quality assurance of malaria microscopy.⁵⁷ MPAC members welcomed the reform process but highlighted also aspects that should be attended to. For example, a potentially problematic implicit assumption seems to be that the focus of policy and guidance development will be on technical-biomedical tools as opposed to more holistic strategies. While room for improvement remains and while it is too early to assess the reform, the key point is that an incremental approach to malaria control would propose to actively engage with such reform processes and to harness their potential rather than developing a preoccupation with strategic questions such as a potential malaria end date.

Regarding the increased attention to the work of country offices, the general idea could certainly prove fruitful for the purpose of malaria control. This applies in particular if the malaria-related competencies are improved: as discussed above, the flexibilities of global strategies are most meaningful if there are capacities to tailor them to local contexts. While increased presence of WHO at country level could be a step into the right direction, there is no guarantee that this will be the case. First of all, the country offices cannot focus on malaria only and the contributions of country offices depend on various factors including their size and their relationship with the host country. Secondly, the increasing role of country offices goes hand in hand with an increasing role of regional offices that are expected to supervise the country offices and a decreasing role for headquarters; this change is also evidenced by a movement of staff from headquarters to the other two levels of the organization. This organizational change was at times described as "inverting the pyramid"⁵⁸ and as a consequence of it, various practical questions regarding the roles of and the relations between the three levels of the organization will emerge. With a view to the important dialogue between countries and WHO, there will be the question of to what extent the implementation of WHO guidance will be supported through an exchange between headquarters and countries or if the regional offices will step in even though they do not appear to have the capacity to do so by themselves yet.⁵⁹ Since the history of WHO is a history of

⁵⁵ In the draft concept note towards GPW13 (WHO 2017c) and also in the draft GPW13 that was presented to the Executive Board in November 2017 (WHO 2017b, e.g. 5), there was a lot of emphasis on a "more operational" WHO. While this language has disappeared in the final version (WHO 2019g), the ideas behind it can be expected to remain influential in the course of the implementation of GPW13.

⁵⁶ WHO 2019i, 10–14.

⁵⁷ WHO 2019a.

⁵⁸ The phrase "inverting the pyramid" appeared in the draft GPW13 that was presented to the Executive Board in November 2017 (WHO 2017b, 21). While this clear-cut formulation was no longer used in the final version of the GPW13 (WHO 2019g), it captures the thinking well that still underlies some of the key organizational changes.

⁵⁹ The status of the transformation of WHO was explained in March 2019 in a video conference during which the Director General of WHO as well as the regional directors spoke. Zsuzsanna Jakab, at the time Regional Director for Europe, made a statement that could indicate a reduced role for headquarters in the implementation process: "An important change we are making is that headquarters will get out of the business of providing day-to-day technical

decentralization that has often been criticised and poses the general challenge of aligning the three levels of the organization, this aspect of the reform process will require particular attention in order to harness its potentials and to avoid potential pitfalls – not only with a view to malaria control.⁶⁰

With a view to the WHO impact framework, there is mainly the question of what relevance malaria has received and how it is going to be measured. According to the most recent document that was available at the time of the writing of this paper, the status of malaria can be described as one of low visibility, in particular if the ambitious targets of the GTS and additional ways to measure the global malaria status are taken into consideration.⁶¹ Malaria appears twice in the impact framework. In the context of programmatic indicators and milestones, malaria is operationalized and evaluated along the lines of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3.3: “Malaria incidence per 1000” serves as the indicator while the 2023 milestone is “Reduce malaria case incidence by 50%”. With a view to the triple billion targets⁶² of the GPW13, malaria features as a tracer indicator for the Universal Health Coverage (UHC) index and is conceptualized in terms of coverage with bednets but no further details are given. There is no need to go into a detailed discussion on what further goals from the GTS, what data from *World Malaria Reports*, or what additional indicators would have been useful. Suffice to say that malaria could have been covered in a more comprehensive manner and that it might be worth-while to work towards this end in future editions of the impact framework even though it has to be acknowledged that the impact framework treats all health problems in such a narrow manner. A more comprehensive account of malaria in the impact framework could be an important step towards giving malaria control a more prominent role while it does not presuppose a global strategic shift towards eradication. A more prominent role for malaria within the GPW13 process and its impact framework is not only about measurement as such but could create opportunities for hitherto missed synergies – for example, between the UHC agenda and malaria control.

In addition to directing the transformation of WHO, GPW13 provides guidance for WHO’s work in line with the aforementioned triple billion targets and within the broader context of the SDGs. An incremental approach to malaria control would highlight the need to follow the developments in these areas closely in order to, also in this case, identify potential synergies with the struggle against malaria. This promises not only to enable a more holistic and sustainable approach to malaria control, e.g. by including housing and other social determinants,⁶³ but also helps to move away from the perception that the various global goals and initiatives were competing for resources in a zero-sum game and that highly ambitious individual agendas would be an indispensable precondition for the mobilization of “private” resources for each of them. Moreover, it will be important to follow the continuing discussions on polio eradication and on post-polio transition that are mentioned several times in the GPW13 and continue to feature prominently at meetings of WHO’s governance bodies.⁶⁴ The positive and negative lessons that member states, WHO, and other actors in global health governance have started to learn from the polio experience might prove to be as influential as the ones derived from smallpox and they might not necessarily increase the desire for additional eradication campaigns.⁶⁵

An issue that has so far remained unresolved is the financing of the GPW13,⁶⁶ which overlaps to some extent

support, which is the core business of regions and countries” (WHO 2019h).

⁶⁰ On WHO’s history of decentralization, see Hanrieder 2015a, and Siddiqi 1995.

⁶¹ WHO 2019f.

⁶² „ The triple billion targets are 1 billion more people benefiting from universal health coverage, 1 billion more people better protected from health emergencies and 1 billion more people enjoying better health and well-being“ (WHO 2019f, 2).

⁶³ Degarege et al. 2019.

⁶⁴ WHO 2019d, and 2019e.

⁶⁵ The lessons learned will not only depend on the final result that continues to be postponed but also on the way in which the difficult road of polio eradication and its costs will be interpreted. In the case of smallpox, eradication led to the aforementioned rehabilitation of eradication as an idea but it was still not enthusiastically embraced. Even Donald Henderson who had led the eradication effort had mixed feelings about eradication (Henderson 1998 and Stepan 2011). Moreover, as evidenced in repeated discussions in WHO governance bodies, the whole issue of post-polio transition raises many difficult questions (see also Taylor 2018). With a view to malaria eradication, recent discussion at the Executive Board suggest that member states take a cautious stance towards it (WHO 2017a, 28–33).

⁶⁶ Resolution WHA71.1 states explicitly “that approval of the Thirteenth General Programme of Work, 2019–2023 does not imply approval of the financial estimate contained in document EB142/3 Add.2” (WHO 2018b).

with the financial requirements for the health-related SDGs and consequently contains also malaria-related expenses. Akin to the aforementioned *Malaria Eradication: A Plea for Health*,⁶⁷ WHO has prepared a document entitled *A Healthier Humanity: The WHO Investment Case for 2019-2023*⁶⁸ and is generally investigating new ways to finance its work, including the creation of a WHO foundation.⁶⁹ These efforts aim not only at increasing the overall funding for WHO but also at a reduction of earmarked funding as well as at a broadening of WHO's donor base. While it is too early to judge the general successes of this process as well as its potential consequences for malaria funding, three observations can already be made at this point that emerge against the background of the previously discussed historical experiences and in light of the literature that highlights the political dimension of WHO financing.⁷⁰ Firstly, it seems unlikely that the general challenge will be resolved that a large part of the funding is provided on a voluntary basis. This means that parts of WHO's work will also in the future be exposed to the danger that funding dries up. Secondly and relatedly, it is likely that the provision of funding will remain an avenue through which the activities of the organization can be influenced – be it by hindering activities through the withholding of funding, by initiating activities via providing (earmarked) funding, by changing incentive structures through funding, or more complex forms of informal governance; also, financial influencing can, in principle, occur both intentionally or unintentionally. Thirdly, while the broadening of the donor base promises to make WHO less dependent on specific donors, it might also increase the amount of actors who – through their funding – influence organizational activities. The implications of these developments for malaria control are not entirely clear yet but a broadening of the global donor base for malaria promises to have similar effects as in global health in general, including a reduction of dependence on specific donors.

A final issue regarding present dynamics is the question of whether any changes can be expected regarding the general structure of the global health governance architecture and regarding WHO's role within it. While GPW13 clearly conveys the message that WHO is ready to take on a leadership role in global health governance, the financial dimension hints at a more complex situation as we have just seen. Moreover, WHO's formal authority is going to remain constrained along the lines that were discussed above: health will generally remain based on “soft law” and WHO's governance bodies can primarily encourage member states to follow WHO's policies. Nevertheless, the recent call to develop a “Global Action Plan for Healthy Lives and Well-being for All” that reaffirms WHO's pivotal role in global health and aims to align the policies of key health-related actors around SDG 3, can be seen an attempt to support WHO in its ambition to regain some of the ground that has previously been lost vis-à-vis other organizations.⁷¹ With a view to global malaria governance it can be expected that WHO will remain a key player and central platform but that exit-based policies will also continue to play a role. Moreover, as discussed above, there is always a thin line between complementarity and competition. Recently, this was evidenced when in parallel to SAGme a Lancet Commission on Malaria Eradication was set up that declared to complement the work of SAGme but can also be seen as a way to bypass SAGme and to subsequently co-opt the discussions.⁷² The latter interpretation is supported by the observation that the Lancet Commission did not wait for SAGme to conclude its work, skipped over more fundamental questions such as feasibility, and addressed challenges like developing a roadmap and calculating the costs directly, which logically presuppose feasibility. While this suggests that WHO's leadership in global malaria governance will remain challenged also in the future, the lesson from the decision in 1955 is that it is advisable to separate the desire to take on a leadership role from the question of whether it is prudent to start a global malaria eradication campaign. In light of the existing tensions around grand strategy in the struggle against malaria, it seems that WHO and its member states can make a valuable contribution by clearly stating where they are standing and heading. Since the agreed goals and targets are already ambitious, even “merely” putting malaria control back on track and following up on existing commitments can make a difference. It will be possible to focus on current challenges and to harness the potentials of some of the present dynamics as outlined in this section. Moreover, the vision of eradication remains intact and an incremental approach that builds on the current global strategy provides enough flexibilities for ambitious countries that want to move to elimination.

⁶⁷ WHO 1958.

⁶⁸ WHO 2018a.

⁶⁹ Ravelo 2018, 2019.

⁷⁰ Chorev 2012, Lee 2009, Reddy, Mazhar, and Lencucha 2018, Siddiqi 1995, Stone 2011, and Vaughan et al. 1996.

⁷¹ For online information on the current state of the process, see WHO 2019c.

⁷² Chen et al. 2018 and Cheney 2018.

5 Conclusion

Malaria eradication *as a vision* has been a recurrent if not a constant companion of modern measures against malaria and it is important to note that SAGme has not been presented with any evidence that would have made it necessary to abandon this vision.⁷³ From a conceptual perspective, neither existing challenges of malaria control nor zoonotic malaria make it impossible to eradicate human malaria. What is more difficult to determine are the exact lines along which the global malaria situation and the factors that have an impact on malaria prevalence (e.g. climate change) will develop over the next decades. This is one of the reasons for which it does not seem possible at this point to formulate a precise and reliable work plan on the basis of which eradication of human malaria could be achieved. By the same token, it is not possible to conclusively calculate what malaria eradication will actually cost; it is only possible to state what the costs were if a set of assumptions held. In other words, it seems premature to turn the vision of a world free of malaria into a goal with a definite target.

In line with these observations, the analysis of the socio-political context of global policies against malaria suggests that it is key to distinguish between two aspects of malaria eradication: the general question of *conceptual feasibility* and the current status of *practical feasibility* (or actionability). While both the history of global efforts against malaria and the theoretical-conceptual literature offer several lines of argument why conceptual and practical feasibility should not be conflated, a central concern could be summarized in the following way: in global health, there is no lack of (non-binding) inspirational and aspirational documents but there is a multitude of obstacles that make it challenging to follow up on these documents. The gap between decisions and implementation has also been noted by policy makers themselves and the contemporary socio-political context offers consequently the opportunity to reduce the size of this gap. Similarly, the Sustainable Development Goals provide a chance to take a more comprehensive and multi-sectorial approach towards malaria control.

From this perspective, the time and energy of the malaria community will be well invested if it harnesses these opportunities and focuses on immediate challenges such as avoiding setbacks and making malaria control sustainable. This focus on the present situation does not mean that the future should be disregarded but it highlights that (disagreement on) long-term projections should not distract from what can be done now. While it has proven challenging to anticipate malaria scenarios for 2040, 2050, or beyond, there are agreed goals, targets, and milestones that help to monitor and evaluate current developments and to formulate scenarios for the upcoming years. As evidenced by the recent “High burden to high impact” approach, a close monitoring of current developments makes it also possible to take action when malaria control gets off track. This is not to say that long-term projections are irrelevant but they have to be treated with caution.

History has shown that the unpredictability of the fight against malaria has to be part of the long-term planning in order to avoid overconfidence. The danger is, however, that a seemingly actionable plan for malaria eradication is promised too early in order to use it as a resource mobilization strategy. A massive underestimation of the costs of malaria eradication was one of the reasons for the failure of the malaria eradication campaign that WHO started in 1955. The misapprehension of the challenge of eradication was not just a result of poor planning but also induced by the deliberate efforts of eradication supporters to downplay the challenges in order to mute the opposition of the sceptics. This is one example for the factors that can lead to a premature move towards eradication and to unintended negative consequences for the struggle against malaria. In order to avoid a situation in which the difference between control and eradication is blurred by reducing it to a mere change in words, the technical guidance that SAGme offers must help decision makers to appreciate the kind of political commitment that would be necessary if they proposed to reformulate eradication as a goal with a definite target. After all, a commitment to eradication means essentially that the effort will be continued even if the original end point is missed and even if the costs surpass the expectations. As Fred Soper has pointed out, there are only two results of an eradication campaign: either success or failure.⁷⁴

⁷³ WHO 2019b.

⁷⁴ Soper 1949, 1173.

Alternatively, a more incremental approach could be taken. Since the vision of a world free from malaria has already been formulated and continues to be conceptually feasible, the central task is probably not to project at what point in time the journey towards eradication will be successfully completed. Rather, the question is where the journey is currently heading and what crossroads are coming up in the near future. An incremental approach uses agreed milestones and targets as reference points and it highlights the need for continuous multidirectional communication around implementation. This includes both local exchanges between WHO and the various actors in individual affected countries as well as global exchanges, for example, around the annual *World Malaria Reports* or around the preparation of normative documents. In addition to continuous communication and annually recurring events, there are other moments at which stock taking and adaptation are particularly apt. This applies to the future discussions both on the 14th General Programme of Work of WHO and on the post-2030 agenda. In the latter case, much of the debate will depend on what GTS targets will have been missed, achieved, or outperformed by then. Such an alignment of policies against malaria with the cycles in which global health governance works will help to leverage developments in other areas, to encourage agreement on actionable policies, and to coordinate the various actors in the malaria space better. Finally, an incremental approach will not prevent individual countries from increasing their domestic efforts in order to meet self-set and ambitious targets.

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